

Synthesis of palladium(II) complexes with semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones using green solvent

Virendra Singh Shekhawat, Sarita Varshney and A. K. Varshney*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : anilakv123@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : A new series of palladium(II) complexes of the type, [Pd(LH)Cl₂] have been isolated by the reaction of palladium(II) chloride with semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones in 1 : 1 molar ratio using green solvent (methyltetrahydrofuran) as a reaction medium. Ligands used in these studies have been prepared by the condensation of semicarbazide/thiosemicarbazide and suitable carbonyls in ethanol. The prepared complexes were isolated as solid product and the authenticity of these ligands and their complexes were established on the basis of elemental analysis, molecular weight determination, melting point determination and IR, NMR (¹H, ¹³C), mass spectral studies. These spectral data revealed that the ligands act as bidentate chelating agent and coordinate via ketonic oxygen or thionic sulphur and the azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal. Newly synthesized ligand and its palladium(II) complexes have been screened against bacterial and fungal growth.

Keywords : Semicarbazone, thiosemicarbazone, palladium(II) complexes, spectral studies, antimicrobial activity, green chemical approach.

Introduction

Methyltetrahydrofuran is an environment friendly solvent. The solubility of MeTHF in water is low, which facilitating easy recovery and reduce variable costs whereas THF is highly miscible with water and generate considerable waste water and waste solvent. MeTHF has higher b.p. (80 °C) than THF (66 °C) so increase reaction rate and save reaction time. MeTHF is an easily dried and low peroxide producing solvent.

Semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones are important class of compounds which have remarkable biological properties, such as antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer, antiviral, antiparasital and antiamoebic activities¹⁻⁷. Due to their pharmaceutical properties which is frequently higher for the metal complexes than the free ligands, they have been extensively studied during recent years⁸. Semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones usually act as chelating ligands and the biological activity of these ligands is related to its chelating ability with transition metal ions⁹⁻¹¹. In this paper, we report the synthesis, spectral characterization and antimicrobial screening of semicarbazones,

thiosemicarbazones and their corresponding new palladium(II) complexes. The structure of ligands are shown in Fig. 1.

(Where X= O and S)

Fig. 1. Structure of ligands.

Experimental

Material and analytical methods : Semicarbazide hydrochloride, thiosemicarbazide, 1-pyrene carboxaldehyde, benzophenone, 4-methyl benzophenone and cyclohexanone were used for the preparation of ligands. Palladium chloride was used as starting material. The chemicals used in this entire work were of AR grade and the solvents were dried by standard method¹². All the reactions were carried out under strictly anhydrous condition. Infrared spectra were recorded in the region of 4000–400 cm^{-1} on a FTIR spectrophotometer Shimadzu-8400S using KBr pellets. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's methods^{13,14} and sulphur was estimated by the Messenger's method^{15,16}. ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ solution on a JEOL AL-300 spectrometer. Molecular weight determination was carried out by Rast camphor method¹⁷. Melting points were measured by the melting point apparatus.

Synthesis of ligands :

Hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of semicarbazide (0.75 g, 0.01 mol)/thiosemicarbazide (0.91 g, 0.01 mol) was mixed with hot ethanolic solution of 1-pyrene carboxaldehyde (2.30 g, 0.01 mol)/4-methyl benzophenone (1.96 g, 0.01 mol)/benzophenone (18.22 g, 0.01 mol)/cyclohexanone (0.98 g, 0.01 mol) in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The content was refluxed for about 2–3 h on water bath and then it was allowed to cool at room temperature. The obtained precipitates were filtered off, dried and purified by recrystallization from same solvent.

1-Pyrene carboxaldehyde semicarbazone [L^1H] (1a) : Dark yellow solid; yield 72%; m.p. 180 °C; Calcd. : C, 75.18; H, 4.52; N, 14.61 (%), Found : C, 75.20; H, 4.53; N, 14.64 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 287.34 g, Found : 280 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1690 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1620 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3170 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ ppm) : 8.69 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}$), 8.96 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$), 3.06 (2H, bs, $-\text{NH}_2$), 8.10–9.12 (9H, m, aryl).

1-Pyrene carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone [L^2H] (1b) : Light yellow solid; yield 77%; m.p. 192 °C; Calcd. : C, 71.16; H, 4.28; N, 13.83 (%), Found : C, 71.21; H, 4.24; N, 13.81 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 303.50 g, Found : 295 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 1062 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1610 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3156 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ

ppm) : 8.63 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}$), 8.81 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$), 2.70 (2H, bs, $-\text{NH}_2$), 7.70–8.43 (9H, m, aryl).

4-Methyl benzophenone semicarbazone [L^3H] (1c) : White solid; yield 76%; m.p. 168 °C; Calcd. : C, 71.05; H, 5.92; N, 16.57 (%), Found : C, 71.11; H, 5.98; N, 16.52 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 253.33 g, Found : 247 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1685 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1628 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3174 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ ppm) : 8.86 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$), 2.96 (2H, bs, $-\text{NH}_2$), 2.40 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 7.90–8.82 (9H, m, aryl).

4-Methyl benzophenone thiosemicarbazone [L^4H] (1d) : Creamish solid; yield 73%; m.p. 174 °C; Calcd. : C, 66.52; H, 5.57; N, 15.59 (%), Found : C, 66.84; H, 5.59; N, 15.71 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 269.39 g, Found : 261 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 1045 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1605 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3144 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ ppm) : 8.57 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$), 2.54 (2H, bs, $-\text{NH}_2$), 2.38 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 7.68–8.58 (9H, m, aryl).

Benzophenone semicarbazone [L^5H] (1e) : White crystal; yield 70%; m.p. 162 °C; Calcd. : C, 70.20; H, 5.43; N, 17.55 (%), Found : C, 70.16; H, 5.45; N, 17.57 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 239.29 g, Found : 230 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1674 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1632 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3150 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ ppm) : 8.78 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$), 2.98 (2H, bs, $-\text{NH}_2$), 7.96–8.84 (9H, m, aryl).

Benzophenone thiosemicarbazone [L^6H] (1f) : Light brown solid; yield 79%; m.p. 170 °C; Calcd. : C, 65.79; H, 5.09; N, 16.44; S, 12.53 (%), Found : C, 65.82; H, 5.06; N, 16.48; S, 12.56 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 255.34 g, Found : 248 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 1035 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1610 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3135 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ ppm) : 8.35 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$), 2.53 (2H, bs, $-\text{NH}_2$), 7.72–8.12 (9H, m, aryl).

Cyclohexanone semicarbazone [L^7H] (1g) : Light brown solid; yield 71%; m.p. 152 °C; Calcd. : C, 54.11; H, 8.37; N, 27.05 (%), Found : C, 54.15; H, 8.40; N, 26.91 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 155.23 g, Found : 147 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1664 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1595 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3125 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ ppm) : 8.24 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$), 2.80 (2H, bs, $-\text{NH}_2$), 2.52–3.44 (10H, m, $-\text{CH}_2$).

Cyclohexanone thiosemicarbazone [L^8H] (1h) : White crystal solid; yield 80%; m.p. 157 °C; Calcd. : C, 49.04; H, 7.59; N, 24.52; S, 18.68 (%), Found : C, 49.03; H,

7.64; N, 24.55; S, 18.70 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 171.28 g, Found : 164 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 1030 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1580 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3110 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 8.11 (1H, s, -NH), 2.51 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 2.42–3.30 (10H, m, -CH₂).

Synthesis of complexes :

Palladium(II) complexes were prepared by the reaction of palladium chloride with ligands in 1 : 1 molar ratio in methyltetrahydrofuran as reaction medium. The resulting solution was refluxed under a fractionating column for 2–3 h. After the reaction, the excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The obtained solid compounds were purified by recrystallization from EtOH 2–3 times and dried by using a vacuum pump at room temperature. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel-G as an adsorbent.

[Pd(C₁₈H₁₃N₃O)Cl₂] (**2a**) : Dark brown solid; yield 76%; m.p. 212 °C; Calcd. : C, 46.48; H, 2.79; N, 9.03; Cl, 15.28 (%), Found : C, 46.44; H, 2.75; N, 9.07; Cl, 15.26 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 464.65 g, Found : 457 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1670 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1605 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3152 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O}, \text{M}-\text{N})$ 532 cm^{-1} , 458 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 8.36 (1H, s, -CH=N), 8.74 (1H, s, -NH), 2.82 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 7.94–8.76 (10H, m, aryl).

[Pd(C₁₈H₁₃N₃S)Cl₂] (**2b**) : Brown reddish solid; yield 79%; m.p. 226 °C; Calcd. : C, 44.92; H, 2.70; N, 8.73; Cl, 14.76 (%), Found : C, 44.88; H, 2.66; N, 8.75; Cl, 14.75 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 480.81 g, Found : 474 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 1042 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1595 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3138 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S}, \text{M}-\text{N})$ 416 cm^{-1} , 446 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 8.12 (1H, s, -CH=N), 8.60 (1H, s, -NH), 2.34 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 7.36–8.10 (10H, m, aryl).

[Pd(C₁₅H₁₅N₃O)Cl₂] (**2c**) : Light brown solid; yield 71%; m.p. 204 °C; Calcd. : C, 41.79; H, 3.48; N, 9.75; Cl, 16.48 (%), Found : C, 41.75; H, 3.50; N, 9.78; Cl, 16.52 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 430.64 g, Found : 421 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1653 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1612 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3160 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O}, \text{M}-\text{N})$ 535 cm^{-1} , 460 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 8.69 (1H, s, -NH), 2.56 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 2.12 (3H, s, -CH₃), 7.62–8.28 (10H, m, aryl).

[Pd(C₁₅H₁₅N₃S)Cl₂] (**2d**) : Black solid; yield 78%; m.p. 216 °C; Calcd. : C, 40.29; H, 3.35; N, 9.40; Cl, 15.89 (%), Found : C, 40.70; H, 3.38; N, 9.46; Cl, 15.94 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 446.70 g, Found : 439 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 1032 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1585 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3128 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S}, \text{M}-\text{N})$ 420 cm^{-1} , 442 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 8.19 (1H, s, -NH), 2.18 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 2.06 (3H, s, -CH₃), 7.10–8.18 (10H, m, aryl).

[Pd(C₁₄H₁₃N₃O)Cl₂] (**2e**) : Orange solid; yield 81%; m.p. 198 °C; Calcd. : C, 40.32; H, 3.12; N, 10.08; Cl, 17.04 (%), Found : C, 40.35; H, 3.16; N, 9.98; Cl, 17.06 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 416.60 g, Found : 409 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1652 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1616 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3138 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O}, \text{M}-\text{N})$ 530 cm^{-1} , 464 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 8.49 (1H, s, -NH), 2.38 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 7.56–8.62 (9H, m, aryl).

[Pd(C₁₄H₁₃N₃S)Cl₂] (**2f**) : Reddish solid; yield 77%; m.p. 206 °C; Calcd. : C, 38.83; H, 3.02; N, 9.07; S, 7.39; Cl, 16.41 (%), Found : C, 38.80; H, 3.08; N, 9.02; Cl, 7.36 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 432.65 g, Found : 424 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 1016 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1582 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3118 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S}, \text{M}-\text{N})$ 422 cm^{-1} , 444 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 8.14 (1H, s, -NH), 2.28 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 7.38–8.56 (9H, m, aryl).

[Pd(C₇H₁₃N₃O)Cl₂] (**2g**) : Black solid; yield 82%; m.p. 188 °C; Calcd. : C, 25.26; H, 3.90; N, 12.63; Cl, 21.35 (%), Found : C, 25.21; H, 3.84; N, 12.60; Cl, 21.30 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 332.54 g, Found : 325 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1648 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1580 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3106 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O}, \text{M}-\text{N})$ 536 cm^{-1} , 456 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 8.04 (1H, s, -NH), 2.54 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 2.35–3.15 (10H, m, -CH₂).

[Pd(C₇H₁₃N₃S)Cl₂] (**2h**) : Dark brown solid; yield 80%; m.p. 198 °C; Calcd. : C, 24.09; H, 3.72; N, 12.04; Cl, 20.36 (%), Found : C, 24.12; H, 3.75; N, 12.07; Cl, 20.31; S, 9.15 (%); Mol. wt. Calcd. : 348.59 g, Found : 341 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 1012 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1556 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3096 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S}, \text{M}-\text{N})$ 418 cm^{-1} , 448 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm) : 7.95 (1H, s, -NH), 2.25 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 2.10–2.96 (10H, m, -CH₂).

Antibacterial test : *In vitro* antibacterial activity of ligands and metal complexes were determined at different concentrations against Gram-positive (*Staphylococ-*

cus aureus) and Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) bacteria by using paper disc diffusion method^{18,19}. The nutrient agar medium was used as culture medium for bacterial growth (Composition : peptone 5 g, beef extract 3 g, agar agar 15 g, NaCl 5 g and distilled water 1000 ml) and pipeted into petriplates. After the solidification of agar 5 ml of warm seeded agar was applied which was prepared by cooling the molter agar to 40 °C and then added the bacterial suspension.

Table 1. The antibacterial activity of ligands and their Pd^{II} complexes

Comps.	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm) (Conc. in ppm)							
	<i>S. aureus</i> (+)				<i>E. coli</i> (-)			
	200	400	600	800	200	400	600	800
L ¹ H	6	8	10	10	6	8	8	10
L ² H	8	10	12	12	6	8	10	10
L ⁴ H	8	10	12	12	8	10	10	12
L ⁵ H	14	16	16	18	13	16	17	18
L ⁶ H	14	18	18	20	14	16	18	18
[Pd(L ¹ H)Cl ₂]	8	10	10	12	7	8	9	9
[Pd(L ² H)Cl ₂]	6	8	12	14	7	9	9	10
[Pd(L ⁴ H)Cl ₂]	9	10	12	13	8	10	11	14
[Pd(L ⁵ H)Cl ₂]	14	16	18	18	12	16	18	18
[Pd(L ⁶ H)Cl ₂]	14	18	20	20	14	16	19	19
Streptomycin	18	20	22	25	19	20	20	23

The compounds were dissolved in DMSO to prepare solutions of 200 and 400 ppm. Disc of Whatman paper No. 1 (5 mm diameter) were soaked in these solutions and placed on the medium previously seeded with tested organism in petridishes. These petriplates were stored in an incubator at 30±2 °C. After 24 h, zone of inhibition formed around each disc and measured accurately in mm. Streptomycin was used as reference compound for antibacterial activity.

Antifungal test : Antifungal activity of ligands and their metal complexes were evaluated *in vitro* against *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Rhizopus stonifer* by using radial growth method²⁰. Seven days old culture of organisms mentioned above grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium were used (Composition : potato slices 200 g, dextrose 20 g, agar agar 15 g, NaCl 5 g and distilled water 1000 ml). Requisite amount of the compound dissolved in DMF, was added to PDA medium so as to get a certain final concentration (200 and 400 ppm). The medium was then poured into the petriplate and the spores of the fungi were placed on the medium with the help of inoculums needle. These petriplates were wrapped in polyethene bags containing a few drops of alcohol and placed in an incubator at 30±2 °C. The linear growth of the fungus was obtained by measuring the fungal colony diameter after 96 h. The percentage inhibition was calculated by the equation $100(C-T)/C$, where C and T are the diameters of the fungus colony in the control plate and test plate respectively. The results of these studies were compared with the standard fungicide Ketokenazole.

Results and discussion

The complexes [Pd(LH)Cl₂] were prepared by the reaction of palladium chloride with a bidentate semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazones ligand in 1 : 1 molar ratio using methyltetrahydrofuran. The reaction was found to be quite facile and could be completed in 2–3 h of refluxing. All the newly synthesized complexes are obtained in the form of coloured solid and the colour of complexes are associated with the presence of chromophoric azomethine group (-C=N).

They are hygroscopic in atmosphere and soluble in most of the organic solvents. The analytical data of complexes show 1 : 1 metal to ligand ratio and monomeric nature revealed by molecular weight determination.

Table 2. Antifungal activity of the ligands and their palladium(II) complexes

Micro organisms		L ⁵ H		L ⁶ H		[Pd(L ⁵ H)Cl ₂]		[Pd(L ⁶ H)Cl ₂]	
		200	400	200	400	200	400	200	400
<i>F. oxysporium</i>	IZ	9	10	10	12	11	13	10	13
	(AI)	(0.45)	(0.45)	(0.50)	(0.54)	(0.55)	(0.59)	(0.5)	(0.59)
<i>R. stonifer</i>	IZ	10	12	12	14	12	16	10	15
	(AI)	(0.47)	(0.54)	(0.57)	(0.63)	(0.57)	(0.72)	(0.47)	(0.68)

IZ = Inhibition zone (diameter in mm); AI = Activity index (inhibition zone of test compound/inhibition zone of standard).

Infrared spectra :

Thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones show intense strong bands in the region $1030\text{--}1062\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1664\text{--}1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band respectively.

Absence of any band due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{SH})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{OH})$ in the region $2500\text{--}2600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3350\text{--}3050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively suggesting that all the ligands remain in the thionic and ketonic form. The strong band due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ is shifted to lower frequency ($16\text{--}32\text{ cm}^{-1}$) on complexation indicating the bonding of metal through thionic sulphur and ketonic oxygen.

azomethine nitrogen involve in coordination.

In the infrared spectra of ligands medium intensity bands appears in the region $3110\text{--}3174\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to $\nu(-\text{NH})$ vibrations. The band observed due to $\nu(-\text{NH})$ stretch is slightly shifted in complex due to probably adjustment of current arising due to coordination of thionic sulphur and ketonic oxygen.

Two sharp bands at just above and below 3500 cm^{-1} assignable to asymmetric and symmetric NH_2 group modes respectively remain unaltered in the metal complexes suggesting the non-involvement of amino groups in coordination.

The mode of coordination is further supported by the presence of the new bands at $442\text{--}460\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $416\text{--}422\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $532\text{--}536\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{O})$ respectively.

^1H NMR spectra :

The ^1H NMR spectra of the ligands recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ exhibit a broad peak at $\delta 8.11\text{--}8.96$ ppm due to $-\text{NH}$ proton. The $-\text{NH}$ proton signal of the ligands also appear in the complexes suggest that this proton not involve in thioenolization and ketoenolization of $>\text{C}=\text{S}$ and $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups and coordination has been taken place in between thionic sulphur and ketonic oxygen to the metal atom. There is no sign of a signal from thiol ($-\text{SH}$) group and of ($-\text{OH}$) group which would be expected around 4.0 ppm and 5.2 ppm respectively, strongly confirm thione and ketone form.

^{13}C NMR spectra :

The ^{13}C NMR spectra of ligands and their corresponding complexes were recorded in CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ solution. The signal due to the carbon atom attached to the azomethine group in the ligands appears at $\delta 161.7\text{--}163.8$ ppm. However, in the corresponding complexes, the signal appears at $\delta 156.4\text{--}159.7$ which indicate the coordination of azomethine nitrogen with the central metal atom. The signals of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ or $>\text{C}=\text{S}$ group carbons

Fig. 2. Addition complex $[\text{Pd}(\text{LH})\text{Cl}_2]$.

where $\text{X} = \text{O}$ and S

All the ligands exhibit a sharp and strong band at $1580\text{--}1632\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the characteristic azomethine $\nu(>\text{C}=\text{N}-)$ stretching frequency. The negative shift ($15\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of $\nu(>\text{C}=\text{N})$ band observed in all complexes which indicate that azomethine nitrogen involve in complexation^{21,22}. Coordination of the nitrogen to the metal atom reduce electron density in the azomethine link, thus lower the $\nu(>\text{C}=\text{N}-)$ frequency in the complex, so this band is shifted to the lower side. The upward shift of N-N band of ligands on coordination also indicate that

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of ligand L⁶H.

Fig. 4. Mass spectrum of complex [Pd(L⁶H)Cl₂].

also show a downfield shift on complexation, indicating the participation of these groups in bonding.

Mass spectra :

The LC-MS of Schiff base ligand L⁶H and their palladium complex were recorded which were in close agreement with molecular ion peaks. The mass spectra of ligand and its complex revealed the molecular ion peak at *m/e* 256.12 and 433.12 respectively, which is coincident with the formula weight 255.34 and 432.65 for the ligand and complex respectively and supports the identity of the structure.

The mass spectra of L⁶H (C₁₄H₁₃N₃S) show main molecular ion peak (M⁺) at *m/e* 256.12 as a base peak (RI = 100%) and (M+1) peak at 257.12. The ligand show other fragment ions at *m/e* 103, 180, 239; which may refer to fragment ions C₆H₅CN⁺, (C₆H₅)₂CN⁺ and (C₆H₅)₂CNNHCS⁺ of mole masses 103, 180, 239 respectively.

The mass spectra of complex revealed at *m/e* 433.12, 435.12 and 437.10 corresponding to (M⁺), (M+2), (M+4) peak respectively and confirmed that complex contains 2 chlorine atoms. It also show peak at *m/e* 376.12 as a base peak (RI = 100%) due to loss of (-CSNH₂) group.

Antimicrobial activity :

These semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazones ligands and their palladium(II) complexes screened for antibacterial (*S. aureus*, *E. coli*) and antifungal (*F. oxysporium*, *R. stonifer*) activity. It has been found that the ligands and metal complexes exhibit strong activity against the test pathogenic bacteria and moderate activity against the test fungi. Benzophenone thiosemicarbazone and their palladium complex show more antimicrobial activity than others.

Conclusion

In our present studies we have synthesized some new semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazones ligands and their palladium(II) complexes screened for antibacterial activity as well as antifungal activity. The more investigations are going on with this hope that some of these compounds may be used as antimicrobial agent.

MeTHF contribute to green chemistry through a re-

duction in the total amount of solvent used, waste water and waste solvent created, due to its unique properties such as high b.p., high hydrophobicity and low peroxide formation. It can save process time and reduce variable costs due to its high recovery rate.

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